

ONLY ONE-THIRD OF PROTECTED AREAS IN THE CHACO EFFECTIVELY CURB WOODLAND LOSS, BUT THEIR IMPACT EXTENDS BEYOND THEIR BOUNDARIES¹

Pablo Yair Huais ^{a,b,c,d}, Tobias Kuemmerle ^{d,e}, Javier Nori ^{a,b}, Ana N. Tomba ^{a,b}, Javier Maximiliano Cordier ^{a,b}, Matthias Baumann ^d

- a Laboratorio de Geografía de la Biodiversidad, Instituto de Diversidad y Ecología Animal (CONICET-UNC), Córdoba, Argentina
- b Centro de Zoología Aplicada, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, Córdoba, Argentina
- c Departamento de Matemática, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, Córdoba, Argentina
- d Geography Department, Humboldt-University Berlin, Unter den Linden 6, 10099 Berlin, Germany
- e Integrative Research Institute on Transformations in Human-EnvironmentSystems, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Berlin 10099, Germany

Corresponding author:

Pablo Yair Huais

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Abstract

Forests in the tropics and subtropics harbor most of the world's biodiversity and provide essential services but are under high and rising pressure from land-use change. Protected areas (PAs) are a central tool to protect remaining forests, but whether they are effective in reaching this goal is often unclear. Their effectiveness also depends on whether PAs displace deforestation pressure into their surroundings (i.e., leakage) or, conversely, may prevent deforestation even beyond their boundaries (i.e., blockage). However, leakage and blockage effects remain typically unstudied. Here, we assess the effectiveness of PAs in the Gran Chaco, a global deforestation hotspot spanning Argentina, Paraguay, and Bolivia. We used a high-resolution woodland loss time series in a robust impact-evaluation design to assess the effectiveness of PAs, including potential leakage or blockage effects. Our work provides three main insights. First, only ~34 % of the PAs in the Chaco effectively curbed woodland loss inside their boundaries. Second, leakage was rare, yet many PAs blocked woodland loss in their surroundings. Third, our findings were consistent across different countries, governance levels, and PA sizes. Overall, our results highlight a substantial underperformance of Chaco's PA network in lowering or halting woodland loss, likely due to inadequate funding of PAs and weak law enforcement. Yet, the substantial blocking effect we identify here is a hopeful sign for avoiding PA isolation in the Chaco. These findings emphasize the potential of strengthening PA management to leverage conservation impact, inside and beyond their boundaries in global deforestation hotspots.

1. Introduction

Forests in the tropics and subtropics harbor high levels of biodiversity, are globally important carbon stocks, and underpin the livelihoods of millions of people (Díaz et al., 2018, 2019). However, the loss, degradation, and fragmentation of these forests, primarily driven by the expansion of industrialized agriculture, and urban areas, threaten the biodiversity of these forests and their many contributions to societies, including regional and global climate stability (IPBES, 2019). Unfortunately, deforestation is still widespread across tropical and subtropical forests, including many emerging and accelerating deforestation frontier regions (Buchadas et al., 2022; Hansen et al., 2013; Pacheco et al., 2021). Pressure on forests is assumed to stay high as it is mainly driven by actors producing agricultural or forestry commodities for international markets, and demand for such commodities is expected to grow further (Henders et al., 2015; Pendrill et al., 2019). Therefore, limiting deforestation by protecting remaining forests in the tropics and subtropics has become an international priority, as exemplified, for instance, by the Glasgow Declaration on Forests (UKCOP26, 2024) and the European Union's Deforestation Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115). Protected areas (PAs) are seen as the main strategy for better protecting threatened ecosystems (Maxwell et al., 2020). Bold targets to enlarge the global coverage of protected lands, including in tropical forests, have recently been adopted (CBD, 2022). As of 2024, 17.6 % of the global terrestrial land area is protected as a direct result of national conservation policies and international commitments (UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, 2024). As part of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, 196 countries have pledged in 2022 to further expand areabased protection to at least 30 % of global terrestrial land (target 3), through systems of PAs or other effective conservation measures (CBD, 2022). Importantly, target 3 foresees that current and future protected lands are effectively conserved. Tropical and subtropical forests will only be safeguarded if PAs and other effective conservation measures work as envisioned, which is, unfortunately, not always the case. This is not easy. Properly assessing the effectiveness of PAs requires a critical comparison between the actual deforestation within their boundaries and what would have likely occurred in similar, unprotected areas (Ribas et al., 2021). Historically, many PAs have been placed in remote, inaccessible areas, where arguably even without protection, deforestation would not have occurred (Joppa and Pfaff, 2011; Nori et al., 2013; Venter et al., 2018). Thus, proper counterfactual analysis is essential to determine the true impact of PAs (Andam et al., 2008; Butsic et al., 2017). Where studies have used proper impact evaluation frameworks to evaluate the PA impact on deforestation (Ribas et al., 2021), typically a mixed picture emerges. Unfortunately, many PAs in the tropics are unsuccessful in fully protecting forests within their boundaries, sometimes without any measurable impact at all, and are paper parks (e.g., Cuenca et al., 2016; Laurance et al., 2012; Lievano-Latorre et al., 2021). For instance, in a study on PAs in tropical Andean forests in Ecuador, only 6 % of the analyzed PAs had a positive impact (Cuenca et al., 2016). Conversely, there is also evidence of the effectiveness of PAs in curbing deforestation in other situations (e.g., Andam et al., 2008; Brum et al., 2019; McNicol et al., 2023; Nolte et al., 2013; Soares-Filho et al., 2010). For example, PAs in the Brazilian Amazon consistently restricted deforestation within their boundaries, primarily through PAs with strict protection rather than sustainable use PAs (Nolte et al., 2013). Overall, the effectiveness of a PA has been shown to vary with the year of establishment, size, country, level of protection, and even the time frame over which effectiveness is assessed (Bowker et al., 2017; Butsic et al., 2017). Thus, there is considerable uncertainty as to where and why PAs are effective. Major aspects of PA effectiveness often remain entirely unassessed. Yet, even if the impact of designating a PA lowers deforestation inside the PA, deforestation could be displaced from the PA to its surroundings, a process referred to as leakage (Ewers and Rodrigues, 2008; Meyfroidt et al., 2020). Such leakage would undermine PA effectiveness, as biodiversity loss simply

happens elsewhere. Conversely, the establishment of a PA could lower deforestation within its boundaries and in its surroundings. Such a spillover process, for instance due to the expansion of conservation measures around PAs or because remaining unprotected forest is weakly accessible due to the PA, can be referred to as blockage and would increase the positive impact that a PA has (Fuller et al., 2019). Only a few studies have so far evaluated whether PA presence promotes or lessens deforestation in their surroundings, either at regional (Oliveira et al., 2007; Andam et al., 2008) or global scales (Lui and Coomes, 2016; Fuller et al., 2019; Ford et al., 2020). These studies have shown highly heterogeneous spillover outcomes, ranging from negligible leakage (Andam et al., 2008) to considerable evidence for leakage (Oliveira et al., 2007), as well as varying outcomes of blockage, including limited (Andam et al., 2008) to widespread blockage (de Assis Barros et al., 2022). Tropical and subtropical dry forests and woodlands are under high and rising deforestation pressure in many parts of the world yet remain weakly protected (Blackie et al., 2014; Buchadas et al., 2022; Parr et al., 2014; Prieto-Torres et al., 2021; Schröder et al., 2021). Generally, tropical dry forest regions are often under the radar of science, conservation policymaking, and funding (Levers et al., 2024; Pratzler et al., 2023). The Chaco, South America's largest dry forest, is one such region experiencing widespread land-use change, mainly driven by Biological Conservation 308 (2025) 111196 agribusiness expansion (Baumann et al., 2022), rendering it a global deforestation hotspot (Hansen et al., 2013; Pacheco et al., 2021) and defaunation (Periago et al., 2015; Romero-Muñoz et al., 2020; Romero-Muñoz et al., 2021). The Chaco has a sparse PA network, with only 11.4% protected (Prieto-Torres et al., 2022) and thus is in urgent need of expanding PA networks. However, it also remains unclear whether existing PAs achieve their objective of limiting deforestation. Likewise, possible leakage and blockage effects have never been assessed. This is unfortunate, as the Chaco, extending into three countries with different institutional setups, laws, deforestation trajectories, as well as PAs networks, provides a unique setting to better understand the conditions leading to PA effectiveness and how PAs link to potential spillover effects. Here, we capitalize on these opportunities by using a quasi experimental, causal inference framework and a high-resolution, consistent time series of woodland loss, dating back to 1985, before the onset of the drastic wave of deforestation (Baumann et al., 2022). Specifically, we ask the following research questions: 1) Have PAs in the Chaco been effective in restricting woodland loss inside their boundaries in the period 1985 to 2022? 2) How have PAs in the Chaco influenced woodland loss in their local surroundings? 3) Do PA effectiveness and possible spillover effects vary across countries, governance levels, PA protection levels, PA age or PA size?

2. Methods

2.1. Study area

The Chaco is a 1.1 million km² ecoregion in South America, extending through Argentina, Bolivia and Paraguay (Fig. 1). The Chaco is subdivided into the dry Chaco in the west, where xerophyllous forests are dominant, and the wet Chaco in the east, where wetlands, palm savannas and grasslands are more common and form a diverse mosaic of natural vegetation (Bucher, 1982). The Chaco has high biodiversity, including approximately 145 mammal and >400 bird species, and it harbors many endemic species with unique phylogenetic histories (IUCN, 2021). The Chaco has a long land-use history, with Indigenous People using the Chaco landscape for Millennia and smallholder settlers occupying parts of the Chaco for centuries (Camino et al., 2018; Nepstad et al., 2006). However, although smallholders continue to be important landuse actors (Levers et al., 2021), the aggressive expansion of large-scale

agribusinesses has happened over wide areas since the 1990s. Growing international demands, the introduction of genetically modified soybean variants during the 1990s (Reenberg and Fenger, 2011), and the introduction of highly productive pasture grasses (Vazquez, 2013) have converted the Chaco into a prime region for the production of beef and feed crops (mainly soybean and maize), turning it into a global deforestation hotspot in the 21st century (Hansen et al., 2013; Baumann et al., 2017; Pacheco et al., 2021). Analyses of frontier dynamics show an increase in woodland loss from the 1980s until around 2010, followed by decreasing woodland losses thereafter (Baumann et al., 2022). This trend was reverted in 2020, with an again drastic increase in woodland loss thereafter. The most dominant proximate cause of deforestation has been the conversion of natural woodlands to pasture, especially in Bolivia and Paraguay. In Argentina, a major proportion of deforested land was initially used for pastures but later shifted to cropland, and a smaller proportion of deforested land was directly converted to cropland (Baumann et al., 2022). Approximately 11 % of the total surface of the Chaco is formally protected (Prieto-Torres et al., 2022), including governmental Pas (municipal, provincial, and national) and private PAs, totaling at least 151 PAs for which information about their boundaries is publicly available (see below). The number of PAs in the Chaco is unevenly distributed across countries, with Argentina having the most, followed by Paraguay, and Bolivia with the fewest. Similarly, PA sizes vary among countries, with Bolivia and Paraguay having larger PAs than Argentina. Many PAs are already isolated and exhibit a high degree of human pressure around and inside them (Nori et al., 2016; Romero-Muñoz et al., 2020), which promotes further isolation. In addition to the protection of natural ecosystems through PAs, the three countries have other environmental laws aimed at regulating land-use change and deforestation outside of PAs, including but not limited to national Forest Laws in Argentina (National Law 26331), Paraguay (National Law 422) and Bolivia (National Law 1700).

2.2. Analytical framework

Our analytical framework was built around a robust before/after, control/impact (BACI) framework to determine the effectiveness of PAs in curbing woodland loss. This involved four main steps (Fig. 2). In step 1, we gathered a database of Chaco PAs and generated buffer zones around each one. In step 2, we processed an annual time series of woodland loss between 1985 and 2020 (Baumann et al., 2022). In step 3, we obtained comparable units between PAs, buffers around them, and unprotected land outside these buffers. Finally, in step 4 we applied robust impact evaluation methods to analyze effectiveness and spillover for each PA individually.

2.2.1. Step 1: protected areas and buffer zones

We gathered our database of Protected areas (PAs) of Chaco from the World Database on Protected Areas (<https://www.protectedplanet.net>; UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, 2021), complemented by PAs in OpenStreetMaps. All PAs came with the year of their establishment. We classified each PA according to their country of location (Argentina, Bolivia, or Paraguay), governance (municipal, provincial, national, or private), and international management category (*strict* (IUCN categories I and II), and *non-strict* (categories III, IV, V and VI)). PAs that partially fell outside the study area were cropped to the boundaries of the Chaco.

To assess whether the establishment of a PA affected woodland loss in its local surroundings, we determined buffer zones around each PA. Diverse approaches have been applied for the

generation of buffer zones to test the effect of PA establishment on deforestation patterns in PA surroundings, especially regarding the size of the buffer zone (e.g., Fuller et al., 2019; Ford et al., 2020; Lui and Coomes, 2016). We decided to test the potential effect of PA designation on woodland loss patterns in PA surroundings by testing buffers of 5-km and 10-km. PAs and their buffers were matched to the spatial resolution of the woodland loss maps, and we retained only those PAs (and associated buffers) encompassing at least 10 km².

2.2.2. Step 2: woodland loss data

We used an existing annual land-cover time series for the entire Chaco for the period 1985–2020 (Baumann et al., 2022). For this study, we focused on woodlands and calculated woodland loss as the difference between woodland area of year y and woodland areas of the preceding year ($y-1$). The map comes originally at a spatial resolution of 30 m and is highly accurate (overall accuracy of 86.1 %, user's/producer's accuracy for the woodland class on average 90.6 %/96.9 %). We aggregated the time series to a 1-km grid by calculating the extent of woodland and woodland loss in km².

2.2.3. Step 3: obtaining comparable units through propensity score weighting

To estimate the effectiveness of PAs in reducing woodland loss, as well as to evaluate potential leakage and blockage effects, we carried out three comparisons using a treated vs. control approach: (a) PAs vs. unprotected areas (i.e., areas outside of PAs excluding buffer zones), (b) PAs vs. buffer zone, (c) buffer zone vs. unprotected areas. We estimated these effects for each PA individually.

For each comparison, we first applied propensity score weighting (Austin and Stuart, 2015) using a suite of covariates to account for confounding effects and, hence, make the observations of the treated group comparable to the observations of the control group (e.g., PAs vs. unprotected). Compared to other matching techniques (i.e., exact matching that pairs control and treated observations), propensity score weighting assigns a weight to each observation to obtain maximum covariate balance between treated and control units. This is particularly helpful when the total number of observations is limited, such as for small PAs. We obtained weights by considering those potential control cells located within the same province (Argentina) or department (Bolivia and Paraguay), to ensure matched cells were under the influence of the same regional institutions (as well as the same environmental laws and comparable socioeconomic conditions), and within 300 km from the edge of each PA, to ensure that matched cells were experiencing similar environmental conditions.

We selected covariates that determine the probability of woodland loss, independently of whether or not a grid cell is part of a PA: slope, mean annual precipitation, distance to the nearest paved road, distance to settlement, soil organic carbon stock, the amount of woodlands and the accumulated amount of woodland loss (in km²) in the year before PA establishment (e.g., Li'évano-Latorre et al., 2021; Fuller et al., 2020; Ford et al., 2020) (see Table S1 for more information about used covariates). These covariates are informative spatial determinants of woodland loss and agricultural expansion in the Chaco (Baumann et al., 2017; Fehlenberg et al., 2017). We applied the function *weightit* from the R package *WeightIt* (Greifer, 2024) to calculate the weights for each sampled grid cell (i.e., treated and control cells) and estimated the average treatment effect using entropy balancing (Hainmueller, 2012). Entropy balancing uses a maximum entropy reweighting scheme to calibrate unit weights, ensuring that the reweighted treatment and control groups meet a large set of prespecified balance conditions. To

understand the impact of weighting, we assessed the covariance balance before and after weighing (Figs. S1–S6).

2.2.4. Step 4: statistical analysis

We compared the treated and control groups through two types of statistical analysis: (1) Generalized Linear Modeling (GLM) for all PAs established before 1991 and after 2016 (32 in total), and (2) Differences-in-Differences analysis (DiD) (Roth et al., 2023) for all other PAs (72 in total). In this way, at least five years were considered before and after each PA establishment for DiD modeling, considering that the used woodland loss data ranged between 1985 and 2020. We applied the *feols* function from the R package *fixest* (Berge, 2018), and included the weights obtained in the previous step. For both cases (GLM and DiD), we extracted the regression coefficient, their corresponding *p*-values, and confidence intervals. A PA was considered to have a *positive* impact if the coefficient was significantly negative (i.e., less annual woodland loss than unprotected units) and a *non-significant* impact if the coefficient was not statistically different from zero. A significant positive coefficient indicated that the PA had a *negative* impact (i.e., higher woodland loss inside a PA compared to unprotected areas). A PA was considered to have a *leakage effect* on its local surroundings if the annual woodland loss was higher in its buffer zone compared to inside of the PA *and* in paired unprotected areas (significant positive coefficient), whether the PA was considered to have a positive, non-significant or negative impact. To test for *blockage effects*, we assumed that only those PAs exhibiting a positive impact within their limits could logically also result in a blockage effect on their surroundings (Fuller et al., 2019). Thus, we considered a PA exhibiting a *blockage effect* if the PA was effective in curbing woodland loss inside its limits (i.e., positive impact) *and* if the annual woodland loss was significantly lower in the buffer zone compared to paired unprotected cells (significant negative coefficient). Any other combination of outcomes was considered a null effect of PA establishment on woodland loss in its local surroundings.

We calculated the annual woodland loss rate inside each PA and inside 10-km buffers, after the establishment of each PA. We calculated standardized rates of woodland loss (Puyravaud, 2003), which allowed us to compare across PAs established in different years. Next, using mosaic plots to visualize the distribution of PAs across different categories, we compared PA effectiveness across countries (Argentina, Bolivia, and Paraguay), governance levels (municipal, provincial, national, and private PAs), and PA protection levels (strict vs. non-strict PAs). In addition, we assessed whether PA impact depended on PA size and age. Specifically, we applied linear regressions between the estimated model coefficients against the PA area and the year of establishment. In all cases, the area of PAs was log-transformed to reduce the distribution skewness. More details regarding materials and methods can be found in Supplementary Information.

3. Results

Overall, we selected 107 PAs for which adequate control units could be found to test their effectiveness in restricting woodland loss within their limits. From these, 94 and 87 PAs were tested for spillover effects at 10-km and 5-km buffers, respectively. Some PAs had to be discarded for testing spillover effects as no adequate matching cells were found (13 PAs at the 10-km buffer and 20 PAs at the 5-km buffer), either between PA and buffer cells, or between buffer and unprotected cells. The propensity score weighting led to a balanced sample (see Figs. S1–S6 in the Supplementary Information). Our results for the analysis at 10-km and 5-km buffer were identical regarding impact outcomes, and very similar for spillover effects (about 84 % of

tested PAs exhibited the same spillover outcome). Thus, we here only show results for the 10-km buffer (see Fig. S7 for results for the 5-km buffer; and Tables S2–S3 for detailed results of individual PAs). In terms of areas under protection, only ~34 % of PAs (36 out of 107) in the Chaco had a positive impact in restricting woodland loss inside their limits, whereas ~58 % of them exhibited non-significant effects compared to the unprotected counterfactual units (Fig. 3). Some PAs even had a negative impact (9 PAs; ~8 %), meaning they had more woodland loss than expected under a non-protection counterfactual. The annual woodland loss rate averaged -1.31 % across all PAs, and -0.42 % across PAs with positive impact (Table 1). Moreover, the annual woodland loss rate averaged -1.72 % and -2.06 % across PAs with non-significant and negative impacts, respectively. Those PAs with positive impact exhibited the absolute lowest annual woodland loss rates (Fig. 4a). In contrast, PAs with non-significant impact exhibited rates spanning the entire gradient, including low, medium, and high loss rates (Fig. 4a). Focusing on the surroundings of PAs, we found leakage effects to be overall rare (4 PAs). However, we found a considerable blockage effect, with ~21 % of PAs exhibiting such an effect compared to a counterfactual scenario (Fig. 3). Almost 75 % of PAs had a non-significant effect on restricting or promoting woodland loss in their surroundings. The annual woodland loss rate inside 10-km buffers averaged -1.35 % across all PAs, and -0.60 % across PAs with blockage effects (Table 2). Moreover, the annual woodland loss rate inside buffers averaged -1.49 % and -2.74 % across PAs with non-significant spillover effects and leakage effects, respectively. Specifically, the distribution of annual woodland loss rates within 10-km buffers, in relation to different spillover effects, showed patterns like those observed in the distribution of values among PAs with different impacts. Those with blockage effects exhibited the absolute lowest values (Fig. 4b), whereas PAs with non-significant spillover effects exhibited rates spanning the entire gradient, including low, medium, and high annual woodland loss rates. The few PAs with leakage effects exhibited medium to high absolute values of annual woodland loss rate (Fig. 4b). Interestingly, PA impact and spillover outcomes were highly correlated, with 67 % of PAs with a positive impact also having a blockage effect in their surroundings, whereas no leakage was found for PAs with a positive impact. Besides, ~96 % of PAs with non-significant impacts also had non-significant effects in their surroundings. If we consider only those PAs where spillover could be tested, two out of four PAs with negative impacts exhibited leakage, and the other two PAs exhibited non-significant effects in their surroundings. The number of PAs with a non-significant or positive impact on restricting woodland loss within their boundaries was evenly distributed across Bolivia (Figs. 3 and 5a). In Argentina, the number of PAs with a non-significant impact (32) exceeded those PAs with a positive impact (22). Likewise, in Paraguay, the number of PAs with non-significant impact (24) far outnumbered those PAs with positive impact (8). Eight out of nine PAs with negative impact were located in Argentina and only one PA with negative impact was located in Bolivia. All PAs with leakage were located in Argentina. The governance level was not associated clearly with positive, non-significant, and negative impacts (Fig. 5b). Among national PAs, there were 50 % more PAs with non-significant impact (30) than PAs with a positive impact (15). PAs with both positive impact and blockage were proportionally more represented within provincial PAs than within other governance levels. All PAs with leakage were national PAs. Besides, about 38 % of strict PAs had a positive impact (10 out of 26), compared to ~30 % of non-strict PAs (18 out of 59) (Fig. 5c). The size of PAs did not significantly influence PA impact or spillover effects ($p > 0.05$; Figs. S8–S9). Moreover, both the PA area and year of establishment did not significantly predict the effect sizes of impact and spillover effects ($p > 0.05$).

4. Discussion

Protected areas (PAs) are the cornerstone of global conservation efforts (Maxwell et al., 2020) and expanding their spatial footprint as well as ensuring that they are effective are major goals for the coming decade (CBD, 2022). Yet, how effective PAs are is overall weakly understood, with existing research often pointing to mixed outcomes. Similarly, a better understanding of how PAs influence their local surroundings through positive or negative spillover effects is needed (Ewers and Rodrigues, 2008; Meyfroidt et al., 2020). This is particularly urgent for areas of high human pressure, such as global deforestation frontiers (Hansen et al., 2013; Pacheco et al., 2021). Here, focusing on the entire 1.1 million km² Chaco region in South America, a global hotspot of deforestation and defaunation, we leverage a robust impact evaluation framework to evaluate PA impact and spillovers systematically. Worryingly, we show that most of the PAs in the Chaco (~66 %) are not truly effective in curbing woodland loss within their boundaries. However, many PAs that effectively restricted woodland loss inside of them, also had an extended positive impact beyond their boundaries, blocking woodland loss in their local surroundings. Leakage, referring to the displacement of deforestation impact from the site of PA establishment to surrounding areas, was not a dominant phenomenon in the Chaco according to our analyses. Despite minor differences, the overall patterns were consistent across countries and governance levels, with PAs showing non-significant impact and no spillover effects being as common as, or more prevalent than, those with positive impact and blockage. Additionally, no significant patterns emerged based on PA size or age. Overall, these findings underscore the need for targeted policies to improve PA effectiveness, in addition to the equally urgent need to expand PA coverage. Our work also shows that once PAs are effective, their impact can reach far beyond their boundaries, which is a hopeful sign for achieving more sustainable landscapes in the Chaco and likely many other deforestation frontiers. Why do most PAs in the Chaco fail to restrict woodland loss inside their boundaries? Our findings show a great variability in woodland loss for those PAs with non-significant impact. Although the reasons likely vary according to the social-ecological context in which PAs are located, we suggest some general explanations. First, many PAs have historically been established in isolated areas and on unproductive land with little conversion pressure and deforestation risk (Nori et al., 2013; Venter et al., 2018; Vieira et al., 2019). Therefore, the impact of their establishment on lowering deforestation is likely negligible, such as in *Sierra de las Quijadas National Park* (Argentina) and *Traslasierra National Park* (Argentina). Second, if PAs are located in areas of high human pressure, deforestation could encroach if the enforcement of PA regulations is weak, thus undermining PA effectiveness. This might be the reality for many PAs in the Chaco (e.g., Cartes and Yanosk, 2020; Matteucci and Camino, 2012), one of the world's regions with the highest deforestation pressure (Pacheco et al., 2021; Baumann et al., 2022), where illegal deforestation is widespread (Blum et al., 2022; Greenpeace, 2025). Finally, PA downgrading and degazettement are common in many regions (Mascia and Pailler, 2011) and have happened in some parts of the Chaco (Cartes and Yanosk, 2020), thus could explain the non-effectiveness of some PAs, but remains unassessed for the entire Chaco. Consistent with previous work (e.g., Nolte et al., 2013), we found PAs with strict conservation goals to have a moderately higher proportion of PAs to be effective compared to less strict PAs. Although the size of PAs did not statistically explain the observed patterns of PA impact and spillovers, some emblematic, large PAs, such as *Kaa-Iya* (Bolivia), *Defensores del Chaco* (Paraguay), and *Copo National Park* (Argentina), effectively limited woodland loss both within their boundaries and in their local surroundings, which is a sign of hope given rapid deforestation in the larger areas where they are located. However, the PA network of Chaco fails to spatially represent both endemic terrestrial vertebrates and threatened vertebrate species (Nori et al., 2016; Prieto-Torres et al., 2022), including species important for the livelihood of

local communities (Tamburini et al., 2023). In addition, because of land-use change, the loss of structural connectivity between PAs has led to their isolation (Matteucci and Camino, 2012; Piquer-Rodríguez et al., 2015). Large blocks of habitat are important for maintaining populations of large animals in the region (Nanni et al., 2021; Romero-Muñoz et al., 2007). All of this highlights the value of prioritizing the establishment of large PAs when increasing the PA network in the Chaco. Why are PAs in the Chaco exerting a positive influence beyond their boundaries? Our results show that when PAs had a positive impact, many exhibited blockage effects, as found for the Brazilian Amazon and Atlantic Forest (e.g., Fuller et al., 2020; de Assis Barros et al., 2022). Two explanations come to mind. First, the establishment of a PA can affect the development of human activities in its local surroundings, as PA establishment and this exclusion of productive land uses could discourage infrastructure development and thus access to the general area around the PA. This seems to be, for instance, the case in *Copo National Park* (Argentina) as well as in the surroundings of *Kaa-Iya* (Bolivia). Second, the successful application of forest legislation and the active presence of indigenous communities in specific areas around PAs could partially explain blockage effects (e.g., Camino et al., 2018; Nepstad et al., 2006). Yet, the observed correlation between the presence of positive impact and blockage effects suggests that part of the blockage could be mainly driven by the application of conservation measures in the immediate buffer area around each PA, which is commonly determined as an objective during the establishment of each PA. Encouragingly, our analyses showed that deforestation leakage due to PA establishment was rare for Chaco PAs, which contrasts findings from other regions (e.g., Oliveira et al., 2007; Ford et al., 2020). However, it is worth noting that we here only analyzed local leakage effects (i.e., in the local surroundings of each PA), but leakage might also occur over larger distances. For instance, previous work suggests that the implementation of zero-deforestation policies in the Brazilian Amazon displaced deforestation to neighboring ecoregions, such as the Cerrado (Moffette and Gibbs, 2021). In addition, leakage could be temporally displaced, such as in the case of the Brazilian zero-deforestation cattle agreements, where avoided deforestation of early enrolled properties was undermined by deforestation occurring in properties registered later (Alix-Garcia and Gibbs, 2017). Accounting for such telecoupled or temporally lagged leakage effects would usefully extend our analyses but would depend on data links across space and time (e.g., trade flows, property data for agribusinesses, etc.). Importantly, we note that even if a protected area did not effectively limit deforestation within its boundaries or in its surroundings, it may still be impactful in other ecological or social dimensions. For instance, we only assessed woodland loss, but PAs could be effective in protecting other ecosystems, including grasslands and wetlands. On the other hand, PAs are considered cultural landscapes, and some PAs are established for other purposes rather than restricting deforestation, such as to protect the cultural values of Indigenous people and livelihoods or to promote sustainable use of natural resources by local people (Sarmiento-Mateos et al., 2019). Indeed, PAs can benefit local communities near these lands, even potentially alleviating poverty when fair comparisons are made (Andam et al., 2010). A more holistic assessment of effectiveness that includes other biodiversity indicators (e.g., presence or abundance of species of conservation concern or carbon stocks), as well as social indicators (e.g., livelihood, food security, or forest resources), would be highly beneficial (Ghoddousi et al., 2022). This would require systematic monitoring of these indicators over time, which is currently not the case for any of the PAs in the Chaco. Some caveats regarding our methodology must be acknowledged. When matching, to find a proper counterfactual, one must select appropriate covariates from the pre-treatment period (i.e., before the establishment of a PA) affecting the response variable (i.e., woodland loss) or the treatment itself (Huntington-Klein, 2021; Ribas et al., 2021). In practice, some potential covariates are not available spatially, and including too many covariates can lead to not finding enough

matching areas. Although we included many key covariates, all of them commonly used in similar impact evaluations (e.g., Liévano-Latorre et al., 2021; Fuller et al., 2020; Ford et al., 2020), other factors could be relevant. For instance, incorporating data on secondary and tertiary roads could have improved our accessibility indicator. Additionally, accounting for variations in socioeconomic factors, such as differences in agricultural incomes, could have provided a more nuanced understanding of human pressures on the landscape. Moreover, incorporating additional terrain covariates (e.g., elevation) or refining other covariates at a local scale (e. g., soil organic carbon) could have improved the assessment of how environmental factors shape land use patterns and thus conservation effectiveness. Our work adds evidence to studies suggesting a prevailing inefficiency of PAs worldwide (e.g., Maxwell et al., 2020; Laurance et al., 2012; Liévano-Latorre et al., 2021). For the Chaco, we demonstrated that deforestation, the primary threat to the region's biodiversity and cultural heritage is not effectively limited by most PAs, in line with prior work (Matteucci and Camino, 2012; Piquer-Rodríguez et al., 2015). Our findings thus show that establishing PAs in the Chaco, and likely other deforestation hotspots, may not suffice to protect forests. Encouragingly though, many Chaco PAs that had a positive impact also extended their protection to the surrounding areas. This result suggests that when protection is effectively implemented, its impact can create additional conservation benefits at low cost. The global network of PAs is expected to expand rapidly worldwide under international agreements (CBD, 2022), the Chaco included, where a substantial expansion would be required to meet the 30 % target. Such an expansion has the potential to benefit biodiversity and local people massively, even with modest expansions (Nori et al., 2016; Prieto-Torres et al., 2021; Tamburini et al., 2023). Our work thus underscores the necessity and potential of implementing international agreements, such as the 30 ×30 initiative (CBD, 2022), but also transnational agreements or coordination programs between Argentina, Bolivia, and Paraguay. For instance, regulating deforestation-linked commodities by prohibiting trade in products derived from illegal deforestation could significantly enhance conservation efforts. Such strategies are feasible, as demonstrated by the European Union Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on deforestation and forest degradation. Ultimately, without adequate funding for PAs and stricter enforcement of existing legislation—either within each country or through transnational coordination programs—expanding the Chaco PA network alone will be insufficient, ultimately failing to safeguard biodiversity and people.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111196>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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FIG. 1.

The Chaco ecoregion in South America spans into: Argentina, Bolivia, and Paraguay. The map shows woodland cover in 1985 in gray tones (% at ~1 km grain) (Baumann et al., 2022), the current PA network, and the year of PA designation.

FIG. 2.

Analytical framework to determine the effectiveness of PAs and potential spillover effects in the Chaco.

FIG. 3.

PA outcomes in the Chaco. (a) Impact analysis (positive, non-significant, or negative impacts) and (b) spillover effects (blockage, non-significant effects, or leakage) of 107 and 94 PAs in the Chaco, respectively. Untested PAs for impact analysis and spillover effects are shown in light brown. The background map shows the percentage of woodlands in 1985. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

FIG. 4.

Annual woodland loss rate (%) (a) within PAs boundaries and (b) within 10-km buffers, in relation to PAs with different impact and spillover effects. Dots depict the value of annual woodland loss rate of each analyzed PA (a) and associated 10-km buffer (b).

FIG. 5.

Mosaic plots illustrating impact outcomes and spillover effects by (a) country, (b) governance level, and (c) protection level. Within each plot, the column width represents the proportion of PAs with negative, non-significant, or positive impacts, in that order. In some cases, the absence of the first column indicates that no PAs had a negative impact. The height of each color block within a column reflects the proportion of PAs exhibiting blockage, non-significant effects, or leakage within a given impact category. Gray blocks indicate PAs for which impact analysis was possible, but spillover effects could not be assessed. The absolute number of PAs is shown in parentheses within each level and within each impact category.

TABLE 1.

	All PAs	PAs with positive impact	PAs with non-sign. impact	PAs with negative impact
Mean	-1.31	-0.42	-1.72	-2.06
Min.	-10.41	-3.05	-10.41	-6.60
Median	-0.69	-0.26	-1.25	-1.76
Max.	~0	~0	~0	-0.50

Annual woodland loss rate (%) in PAs, considering all PAs, and PAs with a positive, non-significant or negative impact.

TABLE 2.

	All PAs	PAs with blockage	PAs with non-sign. spillover effects	PAs with leakage
Mean	-1.35	-0.60	-1.49	-2.74
Min.	-9.67	-5.89	-9.67	-7.00
Median	-0.81	-0.26	-1.09	-1.66
Max.	~0	-0.03	~0	-0.65

Annual woodland loss rate (%) within 10-km buffers, considering all evaluated PAs, and PAs that exhibited blockage, non-significant spillover effects or leakage.